

Enhancing employee engagement: Strategies for boosting job satisfaction

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ABSTRACT

This research aims to analyze the impact of employee engagement on job satisfaction. In an era of globalization and fierce competition, companies must effectively manage their human resources to compete, survive, and thrive. Job satisfaction plays a crucial role in achieving organizational goals through employees. When individuals are satisfied with their work, they strive to perform to the best of their abilities, leading to better job performance and increased organizational success. Job satisfaction is subjective and challenging to measure, as it varies among individuals based on their unique desires and expectations. Therefore, understanding the factors that contribute to job satisfaction is of utmost importance. Employee engagement is one such factor that can significantly influence job satisfaction. Engaged Employees actively contribute to the accomplishment of the organization's goals and ideals because they are dedicated to them. This journal investigates the relation between employee engagement and job satisfaction, aiming to provide valuable insights into enhancing job satisfaction. The research employed a quantitative approach and collected data using closed-ended questionnaires with a Likert scale (1-5). The sample consisted of 48 employees from Private Company in Malaysia. selected through saturation sampling. Data analysis was conducted using simple regression analysis in SPSS v26. The findings indicate a strong positive relationship between employee engagement and job satisfaction. These results support previous research that emphasizes the importance of employee engagement in promoting job satisfaction. In conclusion, this study highlights the significance of employee engagement in influencing job satisfaction. Companies should prioritize strategies to enhance employee engagement to ultimately improve job satisfaction, leading to better organizational performance and employee well-being. Future research should delve deeper into the mechanisms and factors that drive employee engagement and explore additional variables that may affect job satisfaction. Understanding these dynamics can help organizations create a more engaged and satisfied workforce, contributing to their long-term success.

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INTRODUCTION

In the modern era shaped by globalization and intense competition, organizations are required to manage their human capital with efficiency and strategic precision to remain competitive and achieve long-term success. In order for employees to accomplish these aims, businesses must ensure the job satisfaction of their employees. When an individual is satisfied with their job, they will strive to do their best with all their abilities to complete their tasks. Employee job satisfaction has a positive impact on their enthusiasm for performing their work. In the long run, job satisfaction can lead to optimal performance and help organizations achieve their goals more effectively (Ekowati & Ariani, 2022).

Based on research conducted by Mahayasa et al., (2018), job satisfaction is a feeling of contentment towards one's job. However, job satisfaction is subjective and difficult to measure because each individual has different desires and expectations regarding their work (Oksiani & Purwaningrat, 2023). Job satisfaction can be achieved if employees are able to perform their tasks well according to their expectations or even exceed them. Understanding the importance of job satisfaction as a tool to improve employee performance and achieve organizational goals is becoming increasingly crucial. Therefore, companies must strive to create a supportive work environment that promotes employee job satisfaction as one of the strategies to achieve long-term success.

Employee job satisfaction is a critical factor in the context of modern business, characterized by constant competition and change (Kaawoan et al., 2022). With the evolution of time, the paradigm of measuring employee performance has undergone a significant shift. The conventional view of measuring performance based on individual employee capabilities is no longer relevant in an economy marked by rapid technological advancements, quick changes, and intense competition (Munparidi & Sayuti, 2020). Employee engagement has emerged as a key element influencing job satisfaction, where employees who feel actively engaged with their work and organization tend to have higher levels of job satisfaction. However, studies by Munparidi & Sayuti (2020) indicate that only a small fraction of employees, approximately 13%, are highly engaged in their work, highlighting challenges in managing and enhancing employee engagement.

Previous research emphasizes the importance of identifying factors influencing employee engagement. Only with a deep understanding of these factors can managers develop effective strategies to enhance employee engagement (Munparidi & Sayuti, 2020). In efforts to achieve higher levels of engagement, organizations need to consider aspects such as work culture, leadership, communication, recognition, and professional development opportunities. Furthermore, the relationship between employee engagement and job satisfaction needs to be well understood (Ekowati & Ariani, 2022). Higher levels of engagement typically create positive attitudes toward work and the organization, resulting in higher job satisfaction. Therefore, organizations need to focus on efforts to promote employee engagement as a means to enhance job satisfaction, which in turn can contribute to better performance and the achievement of organizational goals.

The concept of employee engagement is becoming increasingly relevant in the context of the relationship between an organization and its members (Neumann, 2018). Employee engagement encompasses aspects of commitment and closeness of individuals to the organization and its values (Munparidi & Sayuti, 2020). When an employee feels engaged, they not only see their job as a routine task but as part of a collective effort to achieve the company's goals. Their presence serves as a motivator for their coworkers to work together towards these goals.

Employee engagement creates a positive attitude towards work and reflects a positive emotional relationship between employees and their tasks (Motyka, 2018). Research has shown that a work culture that promotes high levels of engagement among employees can have a positive impact on an organization's financial performance. Companies that successfully create an environment where employees feel engaged and have a sense of ownership regarding the organization's vision and mission tend to achieve better financial results than those that do not (Motyka, 2018). Employee engagement is not just a management responsibility but also involves the role of employees themselves. Employees who actively engage with their work and organization have a positive influence on their colleagues and

help create a work culture that supports high engagement. Therefore, employee engagement is not just about alignment with the company's vision but also about how individuals actively and positively contribute to achieving common goals (Ismail et al., 2019).

In the broader context, the concept of employee engagement offers the potential to improve overall organizational performance. Therefore, companies must create an environment where employee engagement is empowered and treated as a key element in achieving long-term success. Consequently, employee engagement not only impacts individual satisfaction but also the overall success of the organization. It is important to understand that maintaining employee job satisfaction is a shared responsibility between management and individual employees (Oksiani & Purwaningrat, 2023). Efforts to improve job satisfaction depend not only on the management's role in creating a supportive environment but also on employees' active engagement in their work. In this context, job involvement becomes a key factor. When employees feel involved, they are actively engaged in their tasks and responsibilities, believing that their efforts in the job have a positive impact on themselves (Robbins & Coulter, 2018). They see their work as more than just a daily routine; it is a significant part of their identity. This creates a positive attitude toward work and establishes a value system associated with achieving common goals.

Various studies have shown that higher levels of job involvement are associated with positive outcomes within organizations (Munparidi & Sayuti, 2020). For instance, lower absenteeism rates and lower employee turnover rates indicate that engaged employees are more likely to remain loyal to their company. They believe that their work has value and a significant impact, motivating them intrinsically to perform at their best. Therefore, management plays a crucial role in creating an environment that supports employee engagement. This includes providing employees with opportunities to provide input on company policies, trusting them to complete their tasks, and fostering a work culture that encourages engagement. However, it is also essential for employees to respond with active engagement in their work.

Job involvement is an essential dimension in the scope of the relationship between employees and their work. It reflects the extent to which individuals are psychologically connected to their job and consider the performance achieved as a form of self-appreciation (Robbins & Coulter, 2018). In this context, high job involvement is expected to enhance job satisfaction, as individuals with high involvement see their work as a crucial aspect of their lives.

Based on the explanations provided, it can be concluded that the issues of employee job satisfaction at Private Company are related to the low level of employee engagement in organizational activities, a lack of understanding of customer service and complaint handling procedures, and communication barriers among employees in various departments (Munparidi & Sayuti, 2020). These issues have the potential to reduce employee job satisfaction and the quality of service to customers (Robbins & Coulter, 2018). Therefore, the researcher is interested in conducting research with the aim of identifying the impact of employee engagement on job satisfaction, as reflected in the research title "Enhancing Employee Engagement: Strategies for Boosting Job Satisfaction."

LITERATURE REVIEW

Job Satisfaction

The level of job satisfaction has a significant impact depending on the individual's mental attitude (Priansa, 2019). According to Byars and Reu in Priansa (2019), high job satisfaction can effectively drive the achievement of organizational goals, while low satisfaction levels can pose a potential threat leading to damage. This perspective aligns with the concept that job satisfaction is an emotional state of pleasantness or unpleasantness in the way employees perceive their work (Handoko, 2018).

The level of job satisfaction can have different impacts on organizations. High job satisfaction tends to motivate employees to feel responsible for achieving organizational goals. They are more likely to contribute positively, maintain their work enthusiasm, and uphold high levels of discipline. However, if job satisfaction is low,

it can lead to counterproductive attitudes, such as loss of work motivation and a decrease in discipline. Consequently, employee performance may decline. Therefore, it is crucial for organizations to understand and meet various employee needs to improve job satisfaction levels. This research employs job satisfaction indicators, including (Robbins & Judge, 2018):

1. **Satisfaction with Salary:** Refers to the extent to which employees feel that their wages or salaries are commensurate with the effort and contributions they make in their work. It also involves comparing one's salary with colleagues in similar positions.
2. **Satisfaction with the Job Itself:** This refers to the extent to which an employee's job provides opportunities for learning, growth, skill development, and presents interesting challenges. This satisfaction relates to how well the job aligns with the employee's personal expectations.
3. **Satisfaction with Promotion Opportunities:** Involves an employee's perception of their chances for advancement or promotion within the organization. This includes whether the organization provides a clear career path and opportunities for professional development.
4. **Satisfaction with Supervisors' Attitudes:** This satisfaction is related to the supervisor's ability to provide technical assistance, support, and guidance to subordinates. A good relationship between supervisors and subordinates can significantly influence job satisfaction.
5. **Satisfaction with Colleagues:** This encompasses the extent to which an employee's colleagues are perceived as technically competent and socially supportive. A positive relationship with colleagues can create a positive work environment and contribute to job satisfaction.

Employee Engagement

An important idea in organizational behavior research is job involvement, often known as employee engagement (Robbins & Coulter, 2018). It indicates the degree to which a worker has a psychological connection to their work and believes that their performance there benefits them personally. Predicting employee behaviors like absenteeism and turnover is one of the many important organizational implications of employee engagement. Full-engagement workers typically put forth more effort, attend work frequently, and have lower turnover rates. They see their job as a crucial part of their lives. Conversely, individuals with low job involvement tend to be less participative, less proud of their work, and less satisfied overall. Therefore, improving employee engagement is a crucial goal for organizations looking to create a productive and satisfying work environment. Indicators used to measure the level of employee engagement can be stated as follows (Robbins & Coulter, 2018):

1. **Actively Participating in the Job:** Active participation in the job indicates the level of involvement an individual has in their tasks. Active participation reflects the extent of an individual's attention to their work.
2. **Prioritizing the Job:** Prioritizing the job as a top priority reflects the level of importance an individual places on their work. An employee who prioritizes their job will strive to give their best in their tasks and see the job as a core aspect of their life.
3. **Seeing the Job as Essential for Self-Esteem:** Viewing the job as a vital element of self-esteem reflects how individuals perceive their job as a significant contributor to their self-esteem. Self-esteem serves as a guide for self-confidence and self-respect, demonstrating courage in facing life's challenges and self-assurance in overcoming them.

Hypothesis Development

Engagement in work has been identified as a crucial factor in increasing job satisfaction. Robbins & Coulter (2018) argue that individuals with high levels of engagement in their work tend to perceive their jobs as meaningful and integral to their identity, leading to higher levels of job satisfaction. Furthermore, previous research has found that employees who are actively engaged in their tasks and responsibilities tend to experience greater satisfaction with their work (Kaawoan et al., 2022; Mahayasa et al., 2018; Munparidi & Sayuti, 2020; Oksiani & Purwaningrat, 2023). Therefore, the following hypothesis can be proposed:

Ha: There is a positive relationship between engagement in work and job satisfaction.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

Based on the explanations provided in the previous discussion, The purpose of this study is to examine the connection between work satisfaction and employee engagement.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The research method employed in this study is quantitative research. According to Sugiyono (2020), quantitative research is a research method that utilizes numerical data to measure, analyze, and draw conclusions about the phenomena under investigation. This method aims to generalize research findings and typically involves data collection using specific instruments, statistical analysis, and the use of representative samples. Quantitative research methods are commonly used to measure the relationships between variables and identify specific patterns within data.

Population and Sample

According to Sugiyono (2020), the population refers to all the elements or objects that are the focus of the research. In this study, the population consists of 48 employees of . The sampling technique employed follows Sugiyono's view that the minimum sample size in research is 30 respondents. Therefore, this study utilizes a saturated sampling technique, where all members of the population (i.e., all 48 employees of private company) are included as research samples. This approach allows the research to encompass the entire relevant population and provide more representative results (Sugiyono, 2020).

Method of Data Collection

A closed-ended questionnaire with a Likert scale is used in this study's data collection process. A measurement tool used in research to gauge respondents' agreement or disagreement with particular claims is the Likert scale or questions (Sugiyono, 2020). This scale provides several response options, such as "Strongly Agree (5)," "Agree (4)," "Neutral (3)," "Disagree (2)," and "Strongly Disagree (1)," representing the intensity of respondents' attitudes or perceptions towards those statements. The Likert scale is frequently used to measure attitudes, opinions, or perceptions of respondents in quantitative research. According to Sugiyono (2020), a closed-ended questionnaire is a data collection tool that requires respondents to choose answers from provided options, allowing for more structured data analysis.

Data Analysis Method

The statistical tool utilized in this study is SPSS version 26, which is utilized for basic regression analysis. To evaluate the study data, validity and reliability tests will be performed to ensure that the data used in the analysis are reliable and accurate. In the validity test, the extent to which the questionnaire or data collection instrument can measure the researched variables will be examined. Meanwhile, the reliability test will be used to measure how consistent and dependable the instrument is in measuring the same variable at different times.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Respondent Description

The respondents involved in this research are the employees of private company, totaling 48 employees. The description of the respondents in this study is outlined in the following table:

Table 1 Respondent Description

Information	Frequency	Percent
Age		
20-30 yo	16	33,3
25-30 yo	3	6,3
31-40 yo	15	31,3
41-50 yo	14	29,2
Gender		
Man	20	41,7
Woman	28	58,3
Education Level		
D3	5	10,4
Degree	26	54,2
High School	17	35,4
Working time		
1 - 2 years	6	12,5
3-5 years	32	66,7
5-10 years	10	20,8
Total	48	100,0

In Table 1, based on age, the majority of respondents in this study are between the ages of 20 to 30 years, with a total of 16 respondents (33.3%). The next age group is respondents aged between 31 to 40 years, totaling 15 respondents (31.3%). Additionally, there are 14 respondents (29.2%) who are between 41 to 50 years old. Meanwhile, respondents aged 25 to 30 years have a smaller number, which is 3 respondents (6.3%). Therefore, the majority of all respondents in this study are between 20 to 30 years old, with a total of 16 respondents (33.3%).

Of the 28 respondents (58.3%) in this survey, women make up the majority of the respondents. In the meantime, there are 20 (41.7%) male responders. Women are therefore the study's main group. With a total of 26 responses (54.2%), the majority of study participants hold a bachelor's degree as their highest level of education. Furthermore, 17 (35.4%) of the respondents had a high school education. Diploma holders make up the fifth group of respondents (10.4%). Consequently, the vast majority of participants in this study possess a Bachelor's degree (S1).

In the context of years of service, the majority of respondents in this study have work experience ranging from 3 to 5 years, with a total of 32 respondents (66.7%). There are also respondents who have worked for 5 to 10 years, totaling 10 respondents (20.8%). Meanwhile, respondents with work experience ranging from 1 to 2 years number 6 respondents (12.5%). Thus, the majority of respondents have work experience of 3 to 5 years in this study.

Validity and Reliability Test

Table 2 Validity and Reliability Test

Item	Rhitung	rtabel	Cronbach Alpha	Information
KK.1	0,697	0,285	0,644	Valid & Reliable
KK.2	0,824	0,285		Valid & Reliable
KK.3	0,771	0,285		Valid & Reliable
KEP.1	0,642	0,285	0,806	Valid & Reliable
KEP.2	0,672	0,285		Valid & Reliable
KEP.3	0,839	0,285		Valid & Reliable
KEP.4	0,829	0,285		Valid & Reliable
KEP.5	0,766	0,285		Valid & Reliable

The Robbins & Judge (2018) theory, which includes three indicators—active participation in the job (EE.1), treating the job as a priority (EE.2), and viewing the job as vital for self-esteem (EE.3)—is the foundation for the indicators employed in this study to gauge employee engagement. The derived values (r-values) for items EE.1, EE.2, and EE.3 in Table 2 are more than ttable (0.285), according to the validity testing, which suggests that the items in the Employee Engagement variable (X) are deemed legitimate. Additionally, the Cronbach Alpha value for the Employee Engagement variable (X) in the reliability tests is $0.644 > 0.60$ (Ghozali, 2018), suggesting that the variable is regarded as reliable.

Subsequently, the study's indicators of job satisfaction are based on the theory put forth by Robbins & Coulter (2018). These indicators include: job satisfaction (JS.1), job satisfaction (JS.2), promotion satisfaction (JS.3), superior attitude (JS.4), and coworker satisfaction (JS.5). According to Table 2's validity tests, the items in the Job Satisfaction variable (Y) are deemed valid since the computed values (r-values) for items JS.1, JS.2, JS.3, JS.4, and JS.5 are more than the ttable (0.285). Additionally, the Cronbach Alpha score for the Job Satisfaction variable (Y) in the reliability test is $0.806 > 0.60$ (Ghozali, 2018), suggesting that the variable is regarded as reliable.

Classic Assumption Test

Classical assumption testing is conducted to examine whether the data used in statistical analysis meets the necessary assumptions for specific statistical methods. Classical assumption testing is a crucial step in statistical data analysis because if these assumptions are not met, the results of the statistical analysis can become invalid or biased. Consequently, traditional assumption testing aids in guaranteeing the reliability of statistical analysis findings and precise data interpretation. In this study, tests for heteroskedasticity, multicollinearity, and normality are examples of classical assumption testing. The following is how the normalcy test results are displayed:

Table 3 Normality Test

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test		
		Unstandardized Residual
N		48
Normal Parameters ^{a,b}	Mean	.0000000
	Std. Deviation	2.10245645
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.075
	Positive	.073
	Negative	-.075
Test Statistic		.075
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.200 ^{c,d}

a. Test distribution is Normal.
 b. Calculated from data.
 c. Lilliefors Significance Correction.
 d. This is a lower bound of the true significance.

The results of the normality test indicate a two-tailed Asymp. Sig. value of 0.200 in Table 3 above. This figure shows how closely the data utilized in this investigation adheres to a normal distribution. In the context of the normality test, there is not enough statistical evidence to reject the premise that the data is normally distributed if the significance level (p-value) is higher than the predefined significance threshold (often $\alpha = 0.05$). The assumption of normality for the data can be accepted because the p-value of 0.200 shows that the data closely resembles a normal distribution.

Determine if there is multicollinearity among the independent variables in a regression analysis, the multicollinearity test is used. When two or more independent variables in a regression model have a high degree of correlation with one another, it is known as multicollinearity and makes it challenging to ascertain how each variable

affects the dependent variable separately. The interpretation of the regression findings may be impacted by unstable and incorrect coefficient estimations caused by multicollinearity. Several statistical tests and methods, including correlation matrices and the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF), can be used to identify multicollinearity. The multicollinearity test is shown in the following table:

Table 3 Multicollinearity Test

Collinearity Statistics	
Tolerance	VIF
1.000	1.000

a. Dependent Variable: Kepuasan Kerja

Table 4 shows the results of the multicollinearity test, which is a statistic used to measure the level of collinearity (strong relationship) between independent variables in regression analysis. This test aims to examine whether there are multicollinearity issues in the regression model being used. In this case, the Tolerance and VIF values for the independent variables in the model do not indicate significant multicollinearity problems. Values approaching 1 indicate that the independent variables in the regression analysis are not highly correlated with each other. Therefore, these results indicate that there are no significant multicollinearity issues to worry about in this regression analysis.

To find out if the regression model exhibits heteroskedasticity, the heteroskedasticity test is used. When the variability of the error terms (residuals) in a regression model varies across all levels of the independent variables, this is referred to as heteroskedasticity. Put more simply, it indicates that when the values of the independent variables vary, so does the residuals' spread. The validity of the regression results, particularly the standard errors and significance tests of the coefficients, may be impacted by the presence of heteroskedasticity. It may result in inaccurate conclusions regarding the variables' statistical significance. The White test, the Breusch-Pagan test, and the Goldfeld-Quandt test are some of the tests used to identify heteroskedasticity. These tests look at the relationship between the independent variables in the model and the variance of the residuals. Regression model modifications, such as the use of heteroskedasticity-robust standard errors or data transformation, might be required if heteroskedasticity is found. The results of the heteroskedasticity test are presented in the following table:

Table 4 Heteroscedasticity Test

Model	Coefficients ^a				T	Sig.
	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients			
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
1 (Constant)	3.598	1.127			3.194	.003
Keterlibatan Karyawan	-.183	.103	-.255		-1.788	.080

a. Dependent Variable: ABS_RES

Table 5 presents the results of the heteroskedasticity test in regression analysis. Heteroskedasticity is a condition in which the variability (variance) of errors (residuals) in the regression model is not constant across the range of values of the independent variable. The results from the table show a significance level of 0.080, indicating that at the 0.05 significance level (commonly used), the test results do not show significant indications of heteroskedasticity in the model of regression. To put it another way, the regression model's error (or residual) distribution can be regarded as homoskedastic, or as having constant variability throughout the independent variable's range of values.

Simple Regression Test

To investigate the relationship between one independent variable and one dependent variable, a simple regression analysis is performed. The relationship between the independent variable of employee engagement and the dependent variable job satisfaction is examined in this study using basic regression analysis. Stated differently, the purpose of this test is to ascertain the degree to which work satisfaction inside the company can be impacted by employee involvement. The following table provides a description of the simple regression analysis's findings:

Table 5 Simple Regression Test

Model	Coefficients ^a				T	Sig.
	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients			
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
1 (Constant)	3.416	1.842			1.854	.070
Keterlibatan Karyawan	1.369	.168	.769		8.167	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Kepuasan Kerja

$$Y = 3,416 + 1,369X + e$$

The constant value of 3.416 represents the level of job satisfaction when employee engagement (X) is equal to 0. Furthermore, the regression coefficient for Employee Engagement (X) is positive at 1.369. This indicates that for every one-unit increase in employee engagement (X), there will be an increase of 1.369 units in job satisfaction (Y). In other words, as the level of employee engagement in their work increases, the expected level of job satisfaction also increases.

Coefficient of Determination Test

Table 6 Coefficient of Determination Test

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.769 ^a	.592	.583	2.125

a. Predictors: (Constant), Keterlibatan Karyawan

The regression model's coefficient of determination (R Square) test results are shown in Table 7. The degree to which the dependent variable (job satisfaction) can be explained by the independent variable (employee engagement) is indicated by the coefficient of determination. The degree of employee engagement in their work accounts for roughly 59.2% of the variation in job satisfaction, according to the R Square value of 0.592. This suggests that job satisfaction is significantly impacted by the staff engagement variable. The regression model's R Square of 0.592 indicates that employee involvement has a significant impact on work satisfaction. However, this model's employee engagement variable is unable to account for about 40.8% of the variation in work satisfaction, which could be impacted by other unconsidered factors.

Hypothesis Testing

Table 7 Hypothesis testing (Statistical t test)

Model	Coefficients ^a				T	Sig.
	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients			
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
1 (Constant)	3.416	1.842			1.854	.070
Involment Employees	1.369	.168	.769		8.167	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Job Satisfaction

According to Table 8, the essential t-value of 1.854 (t-table) is less than the t-statistic value for Employee Engagement, which is 8.167. This suggests that Job Satisfaction (Y) is strongly influenced by Employee Engagement (X). Additionally, Employee Engagement (X) has a significance value (Sig.) of 0.000, below the significance level (0.05). Thus, it can be said that there is a statistically significant relationship between Employee Engagement (X) and Job Satisfaction (Y). This finding demonstrates that there is a strong positive correlation between job satisfaction and employee involvement in their work. The more engaged employees are, the more satisfied they are with their jobs..

Discussion

The research findings on the relationship between employee engagement and job satisfaction carry profound implications for organizations operating in today's fiercely competitive and ever-evolving business landscape. This study's primary objective was to meticulously examine the extent to which employee engagement shapes job satisfaction within the specific framework of private company. In doing so, it illuminates the pivotal factors that exert an influence on employee contentment and performance. In the contemporary business arena, where globalization has rendered markets more competitive than ever, organizations grapple with multifaceted challenges. They must strive not only to survive but to thrive in an environment characterized by technological advances, shifting consumer expectations, and economic uncertainties. Consequently, the concept of job satisfaction has transcended its status as a mere organizational luxury and has evolved into a strategic imperative for companies aiming to gain a competitive edge.

Firstly, the results of this research indicate a strong and positive link between employee engagement and job satisfaction, aligning with previous studies' findings. This association emphasizes how crucial it is to create an atmosphere at work where staff members are motivated and dedicated to their jobs. According to Rachmawati (2013) and Kim-Soon & Manikayasagam (2015), workers are more likely to be satisfied with their jobs when they are more involved in their work. This relationship is a valuable insight for organizations seeking to improve employee morale and overall performance. The findings of this research unequivocally establish that employee engagement serves as a linchpin in determining job satisfaction. In essence, organizations that can successfully engage their workforce will invariably witness an upswing in job satisfaction levels among their employees. This correlation underscores the pivotal role played by engagement initiatives in fostering contentment among employees, ultimately contributing to enhanced job performance and overall organizational success.

The modern business landscape, characterized by constant technological advancements, increasing competition, and the need for creativity and innovation, has redefined traditional views of employee performance. Employee engagement has emerged as a central component of organizational success, in line with the findings of Eldor & Harpaz (2016). This research further emphasizes that engagement is not merely a buzzword but a critical factor that contributes to job satisfaction, subsequently impacting the organization's productivity and competitiveness.

Furthermore, this study underscores the importance of commitment to the organization and its values as a key element of employee engagement. As emphasized by Munparidi & Sayuti (2020), employees who are emotionally invested in their company's mission and values are more likely to experience job satisfaction. This insight implies that organizations should not only focus on task-related engagement but also on nurturing a deeper sense of commitment and alignment with their core values. This holistic approach to engagement can lead to a more satisfied and motivated workforce.

The findings also have practical implications for organizational management, consistent with the research of Susan (2012) and Kim-Soon & Manikayasagam (2015). To enhance job satisfaction, managers must prioritize strategies that boost employee engagement, in line with the suggestions of previous studies. This includes creating a workplace culture that encourages participation and active involvement, providing regular feedback and recognition, and offering opportunities for skill development and growth. These practices can contribute to higher levels of engagement and, subsequently, job satisfaction.

In a dynamic and ever-changing business environment, organizations must be agile and adaptable. This study emphasizes that maintaining high levels of employee engagement is crucial in this context, consistent with the findings of Eldor & Harpaz (2016). Organizations need to recognize that engaged employees are more resilient and better equipped to navigate change. Therefore, management should actively seek ways to sustain and nurture engagement, even in the face of challenges or transformations. The investment in fostering such engagement emerges as a strategic choice that promises long-term dividends for the organization, as it directly influences productivity, service quality, and overall financial performance. In the crucible of global competition, organizations that prioritize employee engagement will not only survive but also thrive.

In conclusion, the research on the relationship between employee engagement and job satisfaction, supported by previous studies, provides valuable insights into the dynamics of modern organizations. It reinforces the idea that employee engagement is not a mere HR buzzword but a critical factor that directly influences job satisfaction and, consequently, organizational performance. Organizations that prioritize and invest in employee engagement strategies, as suggested by previous research, are likely to reap the benefits of a more satisfied, motivated, and high-performing workforce. In today's competitive landscape, understanding and leveraging this relationship, as highlighted by previous scholars, is essential for sustainable success and growth. The symbiotic relationship between employee engagement and job satisfaction casts a long-reaching shadow across contemporary organizations. It underscores the imperative of prioritizing engagement as a strategic asset and challenges traditional notions of employee performance evaluation. As organizations navigate the turbulent waters of global competition, they are reminded that the investment in employee engagement is an investment in long-term success.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

In the era of globalization, marked by intense competition and challenges, employee job satisfaction emerges as a crucial factor in achieving organizational goals. The results of this research provide substantial evidence that the level of employee engagement significantly influences job satisfaction, underscoring the importance of creating a work environment that supports employee engagement. In today's rapidly changing organizational landscape, management must view employee engagement as a pivotal element in achieving long-term success.

This study also lays the foundation for future research endeavors that can further explore the various factors that affect the relationship between employee engagement and job satisfaction. Moreover, future research can evaluate the effectiveness of various strategies aimed at enhancing employee engagement and measure their impact on job satisfaction. Thus, this research provides a robust groundwork for human resource management improvement efforts across diverse organizations.

To enhance organizational performance, optimize employee engagement, and boost job satisfaction, companies must recognize that investing in employee engagement is a long-term commitment that yields significant benefits for the entire organization. Consequently, this research serves as a guiding compass for organizations to understand and manage the factors that influence employee job satisfaction amid an era of globalization rife with competition and challenges.

Based on the research findings, several recommendations can be proposed to the management of private company and other organizations seeking to enhance employee job satisfaction through increased employee engagement. First, organizations should focus on developing comprehensive employee engagement programs that encompass various aspects of both the job and organizational life. These programs may include training and employee development, active participation in decision-making processes, and regular feedback channels. Furthermore, creating a culture of open communication throughout the organization is crucial. Employees should feel comfortable voicing their opinions, suggesting ideas, or reporting issues. Management should attentively listen and provide effective responses to the feedback given by employees.

Additionally, organizations need to provide clear and constructive feedback to employees about their performance. This will help employees understand how they can enhance their engagement and job quality. Recognizing and acknowledging employee achievements through bonuses, promotions, or public recognition can also be effective means to boost engagement. Furthermore, fostering a collaborative environment among departments and employees can enhance engagement. Collaboration can help overcome communication barriers and increase the sense of involvement within the organization. Organizations should regularly monitor employee engagement levels and job satisfaction through surveys or interviews to identify potential issues and take necessary corrective actions.

Moreover, it is crucial to develop management skills that enable managers to understand and support employee engagement. This includes the ability to provide effective feedback, manage conflicts, and motivate teams. Finally, organizations should consider measuring overall organizational performance. Achieving high employee engagement levels can lead to better outcomes in terms of productivity, service quality, and financial performance. Investing in employee engagement will bring long-term benefits to the entire organization, improving performance and achieving corporate goals more effectively in an era of competitive globalization.

Regarding theoretical recommendations, several suggestions can be made for future research development. First, further research can delve deeper into the development of employee engagement theory, including a more comprehensive understanding of the concept and the creation of more accurate measurement instruments. The integration of motivation theories such as Self-Determination Theory or Expectancy Theory can also be a useful step in understanding how intrinsic and extrinsic motivations influence employee engagement.

Second, future research can consider integrating a broader range of theories regarding organizational influences on employee engagement. This includes a more in-depth examination of organizational culture, human resource management practices, and policies that can affect employee engagement levels. Comparative studies across different industry sectors or diverse cultures can offer insightful information about the diversity of these factors. Furthermore, the development of job satisfaction theory is also an important recommendation. Future research can delve into the psychological and organizational factors that affect job satisfaction in more detail, helping us understand how job satisfaction evolves and changes over time.

Furthermore, the development of measurement theory is a crucial step. Research can focus more on the development of better measurement instruments to assess employee engagement and job satisfaction. Testing and improving existing instruments should also be considered to enhance their validity and reliability. Finally, theoretical research can explore the generational influence in the context of employee engagement and job satisfaction. With distinct characteristics among generations in the current workplace, gaining a deeper understanding of how generational factors affect engagement and job satisfaction can provide valuable insights.

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